

ADOPTION OF INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTING STANDARDS IN FINANCIAL REPORTING BY ACCOUNT OFFICERS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study assessed the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) in financial reporting by account officers in tertiary institutions in South-East, Nigeria. Two purposes and corresponding research questions guided the study and four null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Related literature pertinent to the study was reviewed. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 849 account officers working in tertiary institutions. A sample of 272 account officers was used for the study. A structured questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha Method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability index obtained was $r = 0.82$. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and ANOVA. Mean was used to analyze data related to the research questions and standard deviation was used to explain how the responses of the respondents varied. ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used to analyze the data. The results showed that account officers adopted International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) in presenting separately current and non-current assets and liabilities in its financial statement position, presents liability in order of maturity and stating balances carried over from one accounting period to the next accounting period in tertiary institutions in South East. Majority of the account officers did not adopt IPSAS in the presentation of current assets in order of liquidity, disclosure of amount expected to be recovered for each asset and liability, receivables and payables from exchange transactions in

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reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South-East, Nigeria. The results also showed that there was no significant difference in their adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities and cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South-East based on type of institution and years of experience. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended, among others, that there should be manpower development by various tertiary institutions to train highly qualified and professional accountants as well as build and develop accounting information system together with information technology. This will help in reporting all statutory income and other internally generated revenue reported for the accounting period.

Keywords: international public sector accounting standards, financial reporting, tertiary institution, account officers

1. Introduction

The low level of accountability and transparency in financial reporting and management in the public sector in Nigeria engenders a high level of corruption due to ineffective and inefficient management as most of the public enterprises have failed to deliver on the purposes for which they were established. Financial reporting involves reporting all statutory income and other internally generated revenue for the period in question. Formal records of financial activities of public institutions are expressed in the financial statements which quantify the financial strength, performance and liquidity of the institution. Financial statements are the core of accounting syntheses, being the most important part of the financial reporting process and the main source of financial accounting information (Berheci, 2010).

The purpose of public institutions preparing financial statements is to obtain and supply useful information to substantiate decisions and to justify how financial resources are used. The four main types of financial statements are statement of financial position, statement of comprehensive income, statement of changes in equity and statement of cash flows. The financial statement of any institution presents the financial position of the institution at a given date. It normally comprises assets, liabilities and equity. Users of financial statements are able to assess the financial soundness of an institution in terms of liquidity risk, financial risk and business risk. Heiling (2011) noted that there is a need for the public sector (tertiary institutions) to maintain quality accounting and reporting systems that are able to accurately reflect these risks.

The preparation of financial statement by public organizations is the only means of communicating an organization's financial information to its diverse parties or stakeholders. John (2011) noted that the manner in which an entity, whether private or public, business or educational, presents information in its financial statement is of paramount importance as financial statements remain a central feature of financial reporting. Most of the accounts presented in the public sector lack proper accountability. The reporting system adopted is restricted mainly to transactions that

have been settled in cash only. Other income and expenditure which have been accrued as well as prepaid are left unaccounted for. Financial statements prepared under the cash basis provide readers with information about the sources of cash raised during the period, the purposes for which cash was used and the cash balances at the reporting date (Ofoegbu, 2014).

Cash-based accounting systems previously adopted by the public sector do not give insight into the actual state of assets, finances and revenues (true and fair view) hence the need to have a clear financial reporting framework for the public sector. Governments all over the world in the quest for proper accountability opted for the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) accrual accounting. The development of the IPSASs has its origin in the accounting profession as a way to improve the transparency and accountability of governments and their agencies by improving and standardizing financial reporting (Deloitte, 2015). The IPSASs accrual accounting basis is hinged on the mode of reporting which takes into account all received income and receivable income and all paid and payables for a given accounting period. Adoption is the process of starting to use a new method, system, law, among others. The adoption of IPSASs by public sector entities is driven by the need to strengthen efficiency, accountability and professionalism in the management of public resources (Nkwagu, Okoye & Nkwagu, 2016).

International Public Sector Accounting Standards are set of accounting standards issued by the International Public Sector Accounting Standard Board (IPSASB) for use by public sector entities around the world in the preparation of financial statements (International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), 2015). Public sector entities are entities that implement public policies through the provision of primarily non-market services and the redistribution of income and wealth, with both activities supported mainly by compulsory levies on other sectors (Tatjana, 2015). The public sector consists of government and all publicly controlled or publicly funded agencies and enterprises and other entities that deliver public programmes, goods and services. The IPSASs is based on International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) issued by the International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) where the requirements of those standards are applicable to the public sector. They also deal with public sector specific financial reporting issues that are not dealt with in IFRS. The Federal Executive Council (FEC) of Nigeria approved the roadmap for the adoption of IFRS and IPSASs for both private and public sectors respectively in July, 2010.

The primary aim of this adoption is to enhance and strengthen the country's financial reporting standards in line with international best practices (Otunla, 2012). In this system of accounting, the financial decisions are not seen merely from the point of view of cash inflow or outflow but also from their impact on the asset and liability position of the government, future funding requirements of assets enabling planning of their timely maintenance and replacement (FAAC, 2015). The adoption of accrual accounting by government entities will help in the assessment of financial performance as the financial statements will reflect all expenses whether paid or not and all incomes whether received or not. One of the financial reporting desires of the public sector has

been to be able to consolidate its financial statements from various government departments in a single line. This dream may only be achievable through the adoption of IPSASs which would facilitate the adoption of a uniform and detailed chart of accounts for the elements of the accounting equation (Tom, 2015).

In this modern technology era, the financial activities of tertiary institutions have increased to the extent that no institution has enough funds to take care of all its needs. As a result, most tertiary institutions have to resort to the adoption of accrual basis of accounting for their general-purpose financial statements so as to ensure uniformity and comparability of financial reporting across institutions. According to the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013), tertiary institutions include universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, monotechnics and research institutions. They are established to meet the nation's need for socio-economic development through knowledge sharing, research and development. The financial reporting activities of tertiary institutions include: collection, keeping and disbursement of various funds, preparation of budget, putting in place adequate internal control system, records of financial transactions (record of assets and liabilities), complying strictly with government financial policies and regulations in the day-to-day financial administrations of the institutions and preparation of financial statements (Osadugba, 2018).

An account officer manages the account of an institution, and this involves monitoring the performance of the account and advising the institution on investments to undertake. Accounts officers in tertiary institutions include Bursars and Directors, Senior Accountants & Auditors, Accounts and Store officers and Cashiers and Clerks (Nwaigburu & Mark, 2014). In tertiary institutions, account officers make sure that the critical financial records are kept for smooth running of the institutions and accountability purposes. Some of the records are students' records, curricular records, evaluation records and financial records which relate to income and expenditure and include receipts for purchases, vouchers, retirements, contracts, donations and budgets. All these are recorded in appropriate financial records for smooth running of institutions. For tertiary institutions to maintain appropriate financial records that will meet global standards, they should incorporate IPSAS adoption in reporting assets and liabilities and cash flow management.

International Public Sector Accounting Standards provide for high quality, robust, and full disclosure of all assets, liabilities and contingent liabilities which are very essential for assessing the true economic implication of public sector financial management. Accrual accounting provides information on an entity's overall financial position and current stock of assets and liabilities. Tertiary institutions need this information to make decisions about the feasibility of financing the services they may wish to provide and demonstrate accountability to the institutions for their management of assets and liabilities recognized in the financial statements (Monari, 2015)

According to the International Public Sector Accounting Standard handbook (2015), cash flow statements present the importance and providing manner of information about the historical changes of cash and cash equivalents of an entity by

means of a cash flow statement which classifies cash flows during the period from operating, investing and financing activities. This information allows the users to determine how the public institutions raise the necessary cash to finance their activities and how the cash was used (Cenar, 2011). The cash flow statement identifies the sources of cash inflows, the items on which cash was expended during the reporting period, and the cash balance as at the reporting date. Information about the cash flows of an entity is useful in providing users of financial statements with information for both accountability and decision making purposes.

The influencing factor in the adoption of international public sector accounting standard in financial reporting in tertiary institutions could be type of institution and years of experience. These variables are likely to affect account officers' mean ratings on the adoption of IPSASs. Type of institution in this study means all conventional federal universities, polytechnics and colleges of education. Federal tertiary institutions are likely to adopt IPSASs first before the State owned institutions could commence their own adoption. Odimmega (2015) reported that there was a significant difference in the views of account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education on the use of accounting techniques and standards. The knowledge, experience and expertise of account officers may determine the extent the adoption of IPSAS enhances financial reporting in tertiary institutions. According to Boger in Ile and Odimmega (2018), Nigerian tertiary institutions do not attract grants from international agencies because of lack of internal transparency and accountability. Boger further stated that experienced accounting professionals can carefully adopt generally accepted principles in the preparation of financial statements in order to ensure transparency and accountability of accounting information. The adoption of IPSAS therefore should be seen as inevitable in tertiary institutions because of its numerous benefits in area of financial reporting, transparency, accountability and meeting global standard.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The IPSAS has been identified internationally as an effective tool for financial reporting. This is why the Federal Government of Nigeria approved its adoption in both public and private sectors of the economy. With this directive, private and public organizations are expected to make their financial statements clear and to make full disclosures of all financial transactions. Despite this directive, public and private organizations seem not to have fully adopted this practice in their accounting transactions. The financial statement prepared by most public tertiary institutions on the cash basis system of accounting lack disclosure of certain expenses that has earlier been prepaid or accrued. Therefore, the cash basis of accounting has not enabled the tertiary institutions to capture all income especially prepaid tuition fees, caution deposits, development levies, identity card levies and other levies. This makes account officers in tertiary institutions not to report transactions that have entered into excess financial transaction above their financial budget. This is probably why their financial statements are lacking both in accountability and transparency and fail to meet the diverse needs of the institutions, hence the need for the standards guiding financial

statements which would remain comprehensive and convey the same information to users across various tertiary institutions in the world.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) in financial reporting by account officers in tertiary institutions in South-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine whether account officers adopt IPSASs in:

- 1) reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East.
- 2) cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- 1) What are the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) adopted by account officers in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East?
- 2) What are the IPSASs adopted by account officers in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East?

1.4 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- 1) Account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East.
- 2) Account officers do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of years of experience.
- 3) Account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East.
- 4) Account officers do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of years of experience.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Adoption

Adoption is the act of accepting with approval, favourable reception, its society, the proposal found wide acceptance (Houghton, 2016). It is the act or instance of putting something into use; the process of checking out the effectiveness of a plan, programme or design. Adoption is a specified set of activities or standards designed to put into practice an activity or programme of known dimensions (Fixsen, Blasé, Metz &

VanDyke, 2013). In the context of this study, adoption is the process of starting to use a new method, new system, new law, among others. It is the implementation of the IPSAS accrual accounting system in line with internationally accepted standards. Adopting a single set of world-wide standards will simplify accounting procedures by allowing an institution to use one reporting language throughout (IAS, 2011).

2.2 Public Sector Accounting

Public sector refers to that segment of the national economy which activities both economic and non-economic are under the control and direction of the government (Gberegbe & Micah in Ibanichuka & Oyadonghan, 2014). Public sector is concerned with providing services to the general public which would not otherwise be available or provided adequately within the financial resources of any individual members of the public, (Bammeke, 2012). Public sector consists of organizations where control lies in the hands of the public, as opposed to private owners, and whose objectives involve the provision of services, where profit is not a primary objective.

Public sector accounting is used by all organizations which are not privately owned and operated, but which are established, run and financed by the government on behalf of the public (Offordile, 2013). According to Adams (2014), public sector accounting refers to all the financial documents and records of public institutions that relate to the collection of tax payers money, and the analysis, control of expenditure, administration of trust funds, management of government stores and all the financial responsibilities and duties of the relevant organs. It includes the process of recording, analyzing, classifying, summarizing, communicating and interpreting financial information about the public sector in aggregate and in details, recording all transactions involving the receipt, transfer and disposition of public funds and property. In the context of this study, public sector accounting is a system or process which gathers, records, classifies and summarizes the financial events and interprets it to provide information to information users.

2.3 International Public Sector Accounting Standard

The International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) are accounting standards developed by IPSAS Board for all categories of government/public sector around the world in the preparation of their financial statements applicable to all levels of government. IPSASs are standards of high quality which serve as catalysts for providing sound and transparent financial statements, thereby improving operational performance, accountability and fair allocation of resources (Acho, 2014). International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) are financial measurement reporting rules recommended for adoption by governments around the world in the preparation of financial statements by public entities (IFAC, 2015). The International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs) are a series of 32 financial reporting and accounting standards issued by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB), which membership spread across 120 countries (Mike, 2014). Nowadays, regardless of different financial reporting requirements or financial characteristics, the

world talk one accounting language through the adoption of unified International Public Sector Accounting Standards, (IPSASs) and International Financial Reporting standard (IFRS) that enhance comparability and international best practices. In the context of this study, International Public Sector Accounting Standard is a modified accrual accounting system adopted by the International Accounting Standard Boards (IASB) to ensure that all revenues and expenditures are properly accounted for to enhance accountability.

2.4 Financial Reporting

Financial reporting is the act of communicating financial statements and related information from a business enterprise to third parties (external users) for sound economic decision making. Financial reporting is the process of producing statements that disclose an organization's financial status to management, investors and the government (Rouse, 2017). Financial reporting involves the disclosure of financial information to the various stakeholders about the financial performance and financial position of an organization over a specified period of time. These stakeholders include – investors, creditors, the public, debt providers, governments and government agencies. According to the Financial Reporting Council (2013), financial reporting is the periodic process of providing information in financial statements (including the notes thereto) about the financial position and performance of a reporting entity to parties (users) external to that entity to assist them in making informed decisions about allocating scarce resources. The objective of financial reporting is to *provide information about the financial position, performance and changes in the financial position of an enterprise that are useful to a wide range of users in making economic decisions* (International Accounting Standard Board (IASB), 2010). In the context of this study, financial reporting is essentially a way of following standard practices to give an accurate depiction of a company's finances, including their revenues, expenses, profits, capital and cash flow for better understanding and appropriate decision making.

2.5 Tertiary Institutions

Tertiary institutions connote institutions of higher learning which comprises the universities, polytechnics, and other allied colleges where both undergraduate and post graduates students pursue a degree or diploma and other certificates with the aim of getting a certificate at the completion of their studies (Ibrahim, Adeyemi & Ayeni, 2016). Tertiary institution also referred to as post-secondary education is the educational level following the completion of a school providing a secondary education. The World Bank (2017) defined tertiary institution as including universities as well as institutions that teach specific capacities of higher learning such as colleges, technical training institutes, community colleges, nursing schools, research laboratories, centers of excellence and distance learning centers. Tertiary institutions, according to Modibbo (2015) are institutions of higher learning where knowledge is imparted to its seekers and researches are undertaken in various fields of human endeavor. According to the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013), tertiary institutions include universities,

polytechnics and colleges of education, monotechnics and research institutions. They are established to meet the nations' need for socio-economic development through knowledge sharing, research and development (Asogwa, Etim & Etukafia, 2017). In the context of this study, tertiary institutions are institutions that offer undergraduate and postgraduate education which prepares individuals to be active members of their communities and societies. Tertiary education is instrumental in fostering growth and reducing poverty.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is based on institutional theory and agency theory. The institutional theory, propounded by DiMaggio and Powell in 1983, considers organizations as operating within a social framework of norms, values and assumptions about what constitutes appropriate or acceptable economic behaviour. The institutional theory states that changes in management practices or culture of an institution to new ones (example: from the traditional cash accounting to accrual based IPSAS) do not occur primarily because of the efficiency or usefulness of the new style adopted but as a result of some institutional pressure. Three mechanisms through which institutional isomorphic change takes place have been identified: (1) coercive isomorphism which stems from external factors like international organizations dictating the use of certain style of management to governments; (2) mimetic isomorphism which is standard response to uncertainty and following the actions of perceived more successful organizations; and (3) normative isomorphism which is associated with professionalization and is concerned with cultural innovations to adopt new styles that are considered superior to the one being used. The relevance of the institutional theory in this study is that changes in organizational structures or style (such as accounting rule choice) do not occur because of the benefits associated with the new style but such changes do occur as a result of the three mechanisms posited above, that is coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism. The institutional theory, though relevant to the present study does not emphasize on accountability in financial reporting. It focused only on organizational structure. To fill the gap, agency theory is considered.

The agency theory was established by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. Agency theory (also known as the principal-agent or principal agency theory/model) describes the relationship between two or more parties, in which one party, designated as the principal, engages another party, designated as the agent, to perform some task on behalf of the principal. The agency theory is used to provide a coherent explanation or rationale for IPSASs adoption in any governance jurisdiction. The agency perspective resonates from the separation of ownership and control in a modern corporation and the fears that the interest of the owners (the principal) and agents (the managers) may not cohere. Accordingly, the theory presumes tension between the principal and the agent, and creates the demand for tension diffusion mechanisms. The use of published financial statements is one of such mechanisms. The view of the agency theory from the public sector perspective is that, a government official is elected or appointed to act on

behalf of the public as an agent, performing the work of directing and controlling resources on behalf of the public (principal). The agency theory, therefore, calls for a strong public accountability between the agent and the principal which can be done through the use of a comprehensive financial statement exemplified by IPSAS.

2.7 Adoption of IPSASs in Reporting of Assets and Liabilities

According to Statement No. 4 of the Financial Accounting Standard Board (FASB) (2010), assets are probable future economic benefits obtained or controlled by a particular entity as a result of past transactions or events. In real terms, assets are resources owned by a business or government. Examples of assets are cash, investments, land, buildings, roads, equipment, accounts receivables, inventories, capital assets (current financial resources) (Alba, 2014). Assets are resources controlled by an entity as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits or service potentials flow to an entity (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2015). This implies that an asset is something that an institution can exercise control over and that future economic benefits must be expected. Tertiary institutions' assets are the accumulated fiscal investments from the State in order to support higher education development. Institution assets serve as the support for higher education development, as well as the foundation and guarantee for tertiary institutions engaging in teaching, scientific research, and management (Wang, 2015). They are significant for improving higher education quality, enhancing the competitiveness of educational institutions, and achieving sustainable development of higher education.

According to Statement No. 6 of the Financial Accounting Standard Board (FASB) (2010), liabilities are probable future sacrifices of economic benefits arising from present obligations of a particular entity to transfer assets or provide services to other entities in the future as a result of past transactions or events. In real terms, liabilities are the rights of creditors or debtors of a business (Alba, 2014). According to the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), (2015), liabilities are classified into current, non-current and contingent liabilities. Current liabilities, also known as short-term liabilities, are debts or obligations that are due within one year. Non-current liabilities, also known as long-term liabilities, are debts or obligations that are due in over a year's time. Liabilities and assets are characterized as rights and obligations. Rights are the rights to receive future economic benefits in the form of cash inflows (resources coming into the organization). Obligations are transfers of economic benefits in the form of cash outflows (resources going out of the organization) (Steve, 2011).

The reporting disclosures of assets and liabilities in an entity's financial statements are measured at fair value. Accruals accounting requires the recognition of all assets and liabilities which meet the definition of assets and liabilities and satisfy the criteria for recognition of assets and liabilities (Brussels, 2013). However, this does not preclude an entity from choosing to move to the full accruals basis by recognizing assets and liabilities in stages. For example, it is possible to focus first on the recognition of short-term assets and liabilities such as debtors and creditors. The recognition of property, plant and equipment would often occur next, although the recognition of

property, plant and equipment may occur in stages with those assets that are readily identified and measured being recognized first. The adoption of accrual accounting would aid the monitoring of government debt and liabilities for their true economic implications. Accrual accounting improves decision making by providing information on full cost of operations and resources used to deliver services to the public and information on assets and liabilities at the end of accounting period (Rkein, 2008).

2.8 Adoption of IPSASs in Cash Flow Management

Cash flow management refers to the management of an entity's cash to ensure sufficient cash to sustain the entity's daily operations, finance continued growth and provide for unexpected payments without unduly forfeiting profit owing to excess cash holdings (Avika, 2014). The cycle of cash inflows and outflows determine business solvency. Cash flow analysis helps to maintain adequate cash flow for the business and to provide the basis for cash flow management (Noor, Nour Musa & Zorqan, 2012). The presentation of cash flow statements according to IFAC (2015) calls for organizations to provide information regarding historical changes in the organizations' cash and cash equivalents. An entity that prepares and presents financial statements shall prepare a cash flow statement in accordance with the requirements of this Standard, and shall present it as an integral part of its financial statements for each period for which financial statements are presented (IPSASB, 2017). A cash flow statement, when used in conjunction with other financial statements, provides information that enables users to evaluate the changes in net assets/equity of an entity, its financial structure (including its liquidity and solvency), and its ability to affect the amounts and timing of cash flows in order to adapt to changing circumstances and opportunities (Ateba & Faan, 2014). In the context of this study, the adoption of IPSAS in cash flow management enhances the comparability of the reporting of operating performance by different institutions, because it eliminates the effects of using different accounting treatments for the same transactions and other events.

3. Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. According to Nworgu (2015), a descriptive survey research design is the one which aims at collecting data, and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The study was carried out in federal tertiary institutions in South East Nigeria. The South East is one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria consisting of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. The population of this study comprised 849 account officers in all the eleven Federal tertiary institutions (five universities, three polytechnics and three colleges of education) in South East Nigeria. The sample size of 272 account officers was used for the study which was derived using the Taro Yamani formula. The questionnaire was structured based on the research questions guiding the study and insight from the literature reviewed. The instrument was structured on a four-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree

(SD). The questionnaire developed for this study was subjected to face validation by three experts in business education. Cronbach Alpha method was used to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument. The computation yielded coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.83 which were deemed reliable for the study. The researchers personally administered 272 copies of the instrument with the aid of two research assistants. Out of the 272 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 263 (representing 96.7 %) were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis.

Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze data in relation to the research questions. While mean scores were used to provide answer to the research questions, the standard deviation was used to show the closeness or otherwise of the responses of the respondents. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The application of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used for data analysis. For the hypotheses, p-value was used for decision making for the hypotheses. Where the calculated p-value is less than or equal to the stipulated level of significance 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$), it implies that there was significant difference between respondents' mean scores. Under this condition, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. On the other hand, if the p-value is greater than or equal to the alpha level of 0.05 ($p \geq 0.05$), the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted.

4. Results

Research Question 1: What are the IPSASs adopted by account officers in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the IPSASs Adopted by Account Officers
in Reporting Assets and Liabilities (N = 263)

Assets and Liabilities	Mean	SD	Decision
1. Presentation of current assets in order of liquidity	2.44	0.77	Disagree
2. Presenting separately current and non-current assets in its financial statement position	2.61	0.77	Agree
3. Presentation of current and non-current liability separately	2.94	0.68	Agree
4. Presentation of liability in order of maturity.	2.64	0.82	Agree
5. Disclosure of amount expected to be recovered for each asset	1.83	0.68	Disagree
6. Disclosure of amount expected to be recovered for each liability	1.51	0.60	Disagree
7. Stating balances carried over from one accounting period to the next accounting period.	2.97	0.68	Agree
8. Receivables from exchange transactions	1.79	0.66	Disagree
9. Payables from exchange transactions	1.63	0.64	Disagree
10. Stating the end of reporting period covered by the financial statement	2.75	0.66	Agree
11. Stating when current liability is expected to be settled	2.79	0.67	Agree

The item by item analysis in Table 1 shows that items 2, 3, 4, 7, 10 and 11 with mean scores ranging from 2.61 to 2.94 are the International Public Sector Accounting Standards adopted by account officers in reporting of assets and liabilities in tertiary

institutions in South-East, Nigeria. Items 1, 5, 6, 8 and 9 with mean scores ranging from 1.51 to 2.44 are the IPSASs not adopted by account officers in reporting of assets and liabilities. The standard deviations of 0.60 to 0.82 are within the same range showing homogeneity in responses.

Research Question 2: What are the IPSASs adopted by account officers in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East?

Table 2: Mean Responses on the IPSASs Adopted by Account Officers in Cash Flow Management (N = 263)

Cash Flow Management	Mean	SD	Decision
1. Classification of cash flows during the period	2.58	0.73	Agree
2. Reporting cash flows from operating activities	2.44	0.78	Disagree
3. Reporting cash flows from investing activities	2.27	0.66	Disagree
4. Reporting cash flows from financing activities	2.29	0.86	Disagree
5. Reporting cash receipts and payments for the acceptance and repayment of deposits	1.99	0.75	Disagree
6. Disclosure of the components of cash and cash equivalents	1.92	0.67	Disagree
7. Reconciling the amounts of cash and cash equivalents in the statement	2.32	0.81	Disagree
8. Disclosing cash inflow from interests	2.86	0.73	Agree
9. Disclosing cash outflow from interest	2.84	0.72	Agree
10. Disclosing cash inflow from dividends	2.67	0.67	Agree
11. Disclosing cash outflow from dividends	1.87	0.69	Disagree
12. Disclosing cash advances and loans made within the period under review	1.98	0.65	Disagree

As displayed in Table 2, the data show that items 12, 19, 20 and 21 with mean scores ranging from 2.58 to 2.86 are the International Public Sector Accounting Standards adopted by account officers in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South-East, Nigeria. Items 13, 14, 15, 16 17 18, 22 and 23 with mean scores ranging from 1.87 to 2.44 are the IPSASs not adopted by account officers in cash flow management. The standard deviations of 0.66 to 0.81 are within the same range showing homogeneity in account officers' responses.

4.1 Result of Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance on the Adoption of IPSASs by Account Officers
in Reporting Assets and Liabilities in Tertiary Institutions in South-East

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	0.968	2	0.484	.077	.926
Within Groups	1703.08	260	6.534		
Total	1704.16	262			

As shown in Table 3, there is no significant difference among the three groups in terms of their responses on the adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East, as the F-ratio (2, 260) is .077 and *P-value* (.926) is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of years of experience.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance on the Adoption of IPSASs by Account Officers
in Reporting Assets and Liabilities based on Years of Experience

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	1.82	2	0.968	.142	.867
Within Groups	1702.23	260	6.534		
Total	1704.16	262			

The analysis in Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference among the three groups in terms of their adoption of IPSASs in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East based on years of experience (0-5 years, 6-10 years and above 10 years), as the F-ratio (2, 260) is .142 and *P-value* (.867) is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Account officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance on the Adoption of IPSASs by Account Officers
in Cash Flow Management in Tertiary Institutions in South East

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	2.304	2	1.008	.140	.869
Within Groups	1958.83	260	7.488		
Total	1960.99	262			

As shown in Table 5, there is no significant difference among the three groups in terms of their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East, as the F-ratio (2, 260) is .140 and *P-value* (.869) is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: Accounting officers in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education do not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of years of experience.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance on the Adoption of IPSASs by Account Officers
in Cash Flow Management based on Years of Experience

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	1.152	2	0.576	.078	.925
Within Groups	1959.84	260	7.488		
Total	1960.99	262			

The analysis in Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference among the three groups in terms of their adoption of IPSASs in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of years of experience (0-5 years, 6-10 years and above 10 years), as the F-ratio (2, 260) is .078 and *P-value* (.925) is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

5. Discussion

The results of the study indicated that account officers adopted International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) in presenting separately current and non-current assets and liabilities in their financial statements, present liability in order of maturity and state balances carried over from one accounting period to the next accounting period in tertiary institutions in South East. Similarly, account officers did not adopt IPSAS in the presentation of current assets in order of liquidity, disclosure of amount expected to be recovered for each asset and liability, receivables and payables from exchange transactions. This implies that most of the IPSA Standards on reporting of assets and liabilities were not adopted by account officers in their financial reporting activities in Nigeria. This finding could lead to inability to control fraud, improper verification and valuation of assets, lack of funds in meeting short-term and long-term liabilities, embezzlement in tertiary institutions' financial reporting in Nigeria.

The findings disagree with that of Ijeoma and Oghoghomeh (2014), Monari (2015) and Balogun (2016) who found that as a result of the adoption of IPSAS by the public entities, there was improvement in accountability, asset management and transparency in financial reporting in public institutions. Balogun (2016) asserted that IPSAS helps in ascertaining the future sustainability of programmes, liquidity position and comprehensive information on the financial position, (that is, assets and liabilities of government can be better assessed). This implies that the adoption of IPSAS in tertiary institutions in South East is expected to give disclosures on accounts of contingent assets and contingent liabilities, disclosures of the amount receivables and payables from exchange transactions so that risks associated with the guarantees issued can be better assessed by the user of financial statements. The test of the first and second null hypotheses indicated that accounting officers did not differ significantly in

their adoption of IPSAS in reporting assets and liabilities in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of type of institution and years of experience. Therefore, it followed that the null hypotheses of no significant difference was accepted. This disagrees with the findings of Monari (2015) who observed that accounting officers differed significantly in their adoption of IPSAS in public sector entities.

The results of the study also revealed that account officers adopted International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) in the classification of cash flows during the period, disclosing cash inflow and outflow from interests and dividends in tertiary institutions in South East. Moreover, majority of the respondents did not adopt IPSAS in reporting cash flows from operating, investing and operating activities, reporting cash receipts and payments for the acceptance and repayment of deposits. Similarly, the respondents did not adopt IPSAS in reconciling the amounts of cash and cash equivalents in the statement; disclose cash inflow from dividends and cash and advances and loans made within the period under review. This implies that account officers did not adopt IPSASs in disclosing cash flows from operating, investing and financing activities which should help the institution to ascertain the future sustainability of programmes in Nigeria.

The findings of the study corroborates that of Ohaka, Dagogo and Bayie (2016) who observed that the adoption of IPSAS has the huge potential of improving transparency and accountability in government financial management. Cash flow statement provides means by which an institution can discharge its accountability for cash inflows and cash outflows during the reporting period. Also Bingilar and Oyadonghan (2014) stated that auditors and accounts officers should use cash flow ratios in evaluating the performance of organizations before forming an independent opinion on the financial statement. This will give detailed information on the organization to enable investors make rational investment decisions and the cycle of cash inflows and outflows determine the institution's solvency and ability to finance its growth from internally generated funds. The findings from the test of third and fourth null hypotheses revealed that account officers did not differ significantly in their adoption of IPSAS in cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East on the basis of type of institution and years of experience. It followed therefore that the null hypotheses was not rejected. This agreed with the study of Opanyi (2016) whose result showed no significant difference in items and that the adoption of IPSAS was adjudged to have moderate effect on the quality of financial reports in public sector. The findings of Bingilar and Oyadonghan (2014) revealed that operating and financing cash flows have significant positive relationship with corporate performance in public sector in Nigeria.

6. Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it was revealed that account officers did not adopt IPSAS in reporting of assets and liabilities and cash flow management in tertiary institutions in South East. Accounting standards are designed to promote global

confidence in organizations' reporting. International Public Sector Accounting Standard is a set of reporting modules of governmental activities to project, promote, protect and sustain good governance globally as far as possible within the jurisdictions that have been adopted. Therefore, it is important that the adoption of IPSAS based procedure and regulations/standards by accounting officers would enhance the provision of more meaningful information for decision makers and improve the quality of financial reporting system in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) The Federal Government should include International Public Sector Accounting Standards in the accounting education curriculum in tertiary institutions. This will help to improve the existing financial management mechanism and policy to enable accrual-based accounting and IPSAS to be adopted.
- 2) Measures should be taken by tertiary institutions to enhance the disclosure of relevant financial information that will help in reporting assets and liabilities. This will facilitate the analysis of transactions (that is, avoiding understatement of assets or the overstatement of liabilities) and stock positions between institutional units and serve as a framework for assessing the sources and uses of financing and degree of liquidity for these units.
- 3) There should be manpower development by various tertiary institutions to train highly qualified and professional accountants as well as build and develop accounting information system together with information technology. This will help in reporting all statutory income and other internally generated revenue reported for the accounting period.

References

- Abdullahi, S. R. (2011). *Mastering cost and management accounting (1st Edition)*. Kano-Nigeria: Gidan Dabino Publishers.
- Acho, Y. (2014). The challenges of adopting international public sector accounting standard (IPSAS) by Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences and Public Policy*, 6(2), 61-68.
- Adams, R. A. (2014). *Public sector accounting and finance made simple, revised edition 3*, Lagos: Corporate Publishers Venture.
- Alba, E. (2014). Beginning governmental accounting. WMCA Workshop.
- Asogwa, I. E., Etim, E. O., & Etukafia, N. I. (2017). Cost control measures and funds management in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 18(2), 1-14.
- Ateba, B. B., & Faan, P. (2014). Cash flow management: Assessing its impact on the operational performance of small and medium size enterprises at the Mafikeng Local Municipality in South Africa prior to the global financial crisis. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(27), 226-235.

- Avika, M. (2014). *The impact of cash management on profitability and sustainability of small retail businesses in the Tongaat area, KwaZulu-Natal*. M.Sc thesis submitted to the Cost and Management Accounting in the Department of Management Accounting, Faculty of Accounting and Informatics, Durban University of Technology, Durban, South Africa.
- Balogun, E. O. (2016). The impacts of international public sector accounting standards in the Nigerian public sector. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Social & Management Sciences*, 2(7), 15-33.
- Bammeke, A. S. (2012). *Public sector accounting and finance for decision making*. 2nd Ed. Lagos, SAB Associates Ltd.
- Berheci, M. (2010). Financial reports capitalization. *Accounting Syntheses: Theory, Analysis, Case Studies CECCAR PH, Bucharest*, 380.
- Bingilar, P. F., & Oyadonghan, K. J. (2014). Cash flow and corporate performance: A study of selected food and beverages companies. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(7), 77-87.
- Brussels, 5.2 (2013). Final commission staff working document. *European Commission*.
- Cenar, J. (2011). Financial reporting in education institutions the implications of the transition to accrual accounting. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*, 13(1), 22-29.
- Dagogo, D. W., & Ohaka, J. (2015). The real impact of financial intervention of enterprise development in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(6), 240-246
- Deloitte (May 2015). *Financial reporting by not-for-profit entities*. IPSAS in your pocket, 2015 Edition.
- Deloitte (2017). *IPSAS in your pocket* (April 2017 ed.) Deloitte.
- DiMaggio, P. & Powell, W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *Journal of American Sociological Review*, 48(1): 146-160.
- FAAC (2012). *Improving the public sector accounting system in Nigeria*. Abuja: FAAC Sub Committee.
- FASB (2010), *Conceptual framework for financial reporting* (Chapter 3: Qualitative characteristics of useful financial information). Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts No. 8, Norwalk, CT.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013). *National policy on education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2015). *Accrual accounting manual for all public sector entities in Nigeria (Federal, States and Local Government)*. Abuja: Federation Account Allocation Committee (FAAC) Sub-Committee on IPSAS implementation.
- Financial Reporting Council (2014). *Guidance on risk management, internal control and related financial and business reporting*. Retrieved from <https://www.frc.org.uk/Our-Work/Publications/Corporate-Governance/Guidance-on-Risk-Management,-Internal-Control-and.pdf>

- Fixsen, D., Blase, K., Metz, A., & VanDyke, M. (2013). Statewide adoption of evidence-based programs. *Exceptional Children (Special Issue)*, 79(2), 213-230.
- Heiling, J. (2011). The importance of research in the field of governmental accounting – Views from a Practitioner. *Comparative International Governmental Accounting Research Newsletter*, 2(2), 89-100.
- Houghton, M. (2016). *The American heritage dictionary of the English Language, Fifth Edition*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt Publishing Company
- IASB, (2010), *the conceptual framework for financial reporting*. <http://eifrs.iasb.org/eifrs/bnstandards/en/framework.pdf>.]
- Ibanichuka, E. A. L., & Oyadonghan, K. J. (2014). A critique on cash basis of accounting and budget implementation in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(3), 69-83.
- Ibrahim, J., Adeyemi, A. O., & Ayeni, A. P. (2016). Critical evaluation of accounting system in tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(3), 63-76.
- IFAC. (2015). *International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) Board, Handbook of International Public Sector Accounting Pronouncements*. New York: IFAC sub Committee.
- Ijeoma. N. B., Oghoghomeh. T. Adoption of international public sector accounting standards in Nigeria: Expectations, benefits and challenges. *Journal of Investment and Management*, 3(1), 21-29. doi: 10.11648/j.jim.20140301.13
- Ile, C. M., & Odimmega, C. G. (2018). Use of forensic accounting techniques in the detection of fraud in tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. *African Research Review, International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*, 12(1), 66-76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/afrrrev.v12.1.8>.
- IPSASB (2017). *Handbook of International Public Sector Accounting Pronouncements*. 2017 Edition, 1. New York: IPSAS Board.
- Jensen, M., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm, managerial behaviour, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 305-360.
- John, C. (2011). IPSAS adoption in Nigeria step to improved accountability in the Nigeria public sector.
- Mike, M. (2014). Implications of IPSAS benefits and opportunities. *CPA*, 8-9
- Modibbo, S. A. (2015). Impact of internal audit unit on the effectiveness of internal control system of tertiary educational institutions in Adamawa State Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education*, 2(5), 140-156.
- Monari, N. K. (2015), *The effect of adoption of international public sector accounting standards on financial reporting in the public sector of Kenya*. (Master's project, university of Nairobi, Kenya).
- Nkwagu, L. C., Okoye, G. O., & Nkwagu, C. C. (2016). International public sector accounting standards adoption and financial transparency in the Nigerian South Eastern States public sector: A case of Ebonyi and Enugu States. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 21(7), 40-51. DOI: 10.9790/0837-2104074051

- Noor, M. I., Nour, A., Musa, A., & Zorqan, S. (2012). The role of cash flow in explaining the change in company liquidity. *Journal of Advanced Social Research*, 2(4), 231-243.
- Nwaigburu, K. O., & Mark, B. U. (2014). The use of accounting information in decision making for sustainable development in Nigeria: A study of selected tertiary institutions in Imo State. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 7(2), 167-175.
- Nworgu, B. G. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology* (3rd edition). Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- Odimmega, C. G. (2015). *Extent of use of forensic accounting techniques in the detection and prevention of fraud in tertiary institutions in Anambra State*. Unpublished M.Sc Thesis submitted to the Department of Vocational Education, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Ofoegbu, G. N. (2014). New public management and accrual accounting basis for transparency and accountability in the Nigerian public sector. *Journal of Business and Management*, 16(7), 104-113.
- Offordile, U. D. (2013). Public sector accounting: The Nigerian experience. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(8), 446-451.
- Ohaka, J., Dagogo, D., & Banyie, J. L. (2016). International public sector accounting standards (IPSAS) and local government financial management in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 2(3), 1-11.
- Opanyi, R. O. (2016). The effect of adoption of international public sector accounting standards on quality of financial reports in public sector in Kenya. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(28), 161-187. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19044/esj.2016.v12n28p161>
- Osudugba, O. P. (2018). *Mandate of the bursary*. The Federal University of Technology Akure. Computer Resource Centre.
- Otunla, J. O. (2014). The implementation of the international public sector accounting standards in Nigeria: The journey so far. A presentation at the Annual Accountants' Conference of ICAN.
- Rkein, A. (2008). *Accrual accounting and public sector reform: Northern territory experience*. Ph.D Dissertation submitted to the School of Law and Business, Faculty of Law, Business and Arts, Charles Darwin University.
- Rouse, M. (2017). Definition of financial reporting. *TechTarget*
- Steve, C. (2011). *IFRS for Dummies*. John Wiley and Sons Ltd Publication.
- Tatjana, J. (2015). Public sector accounting in Slovenia and Croatia. *Public Finances and Accounting HKJU-CCPA*, 15(4), 791-814.
- Tom, O. O. (2015). *The impact of implementation of international public sector accounting standards on financial reporting in public sector in Kenta*. A M.Sc. thesis submitted to the School of Business, University of Nairobi.
- World Bank. (2017). Brief: Driving development with tertiary education reforms. Washington, D. C: Smarter Education Systems.

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